

FAMILY IS THE PILLAR OF SOCIETY

O'tasheva Lola¹

¹Termez State Pedagogical Institute Teacher

Temirova Husnigul²

²Termez State Pedagogical Institute 2nd year
student of preschool education

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7347533>

Annotation: In this article we can learn about the functions of the family before society, their role.

Keyword: family, Society, time, child, parent, man-woman, moral education, physically healthy, morally pure, hard work.

"Raising our children as independent-minded, modern people of knowledge and professions, with a healthy life position, truly patriotic people is an issue for us when it has not lost its relevance," emphasizes the Reverend President Sh.Mirziyoyev. It is known to all of us that the child is brought up mainly in the family. The family, through its environment, constantly influences the worldview and behavior of the child. Ibn Sina, the great allomim, the Sultan of the science of Medicine, argued that "parents start raising a child from a noble task as if they were to give him a name." There is another of our scholars who made a great contribution to the development of the pedagogical field A.And Avlani wrote in his works that it is necessary to first of all worry about the health of the child in this area. In fact, raising children is a very laborious process. That is why education consists only of words and teaching, and upbringing is carried out through practical work and experience.

We know that in the family, humanity is considered a place where people show their feelings, exciting moments and, moreover, their faith and faith. We all understand well that there are many different opinions about the family and its surroundings. We imagine that the structure of the family and the system of multifaceted relations in it consists only of male-female, parental and child ties. But if this is true in one way or another, in the other, I think it is also necessary that we know that this can also cause a superficial view of the relationship. In our conditions, the presence of seed-growing, neighborhood-shirt relations is obvious to brcha. And these are carried out depending on their family living environment, not only having their own influence on family-marriage relations. Because if something escapes in the family, or someone from an adult can argue and disagree, of course, "don't make your voice loud-we will be a neighbor, a person who will say what if he hears a neighborhood" or try not to perceive what is happening in the family to the environment with other words. That is why such families live in peace. In the family, parents achieve the right upbringing through their research, studies and experience. In addition, all qualities in a child mature with morality. Therefore, upbringing also needs to be decorated with good morals. Of course, we know that moral education is based in the family.[3]

We are not mistaken if we say that parents and their personal example are considered an example in this place. Because parents are considered the first caregivers in a child's life. It should also be noted separately that it is necessary for us to travel, taking into account that the child will be very imitative. That is why nothing in the family is considered to be able to influence as a model Force. It is no exaggeration to say that family education will be part of

social education. In this, social, emotional, behavioral and other qualities of the child are formed. The family is the smallest hearth of society, in this place the future person will mature. Therefore, the formation of personality is considered a rather complex and multifaceted process. Family upbringing, in addition to ensuring the general and emotional development of the child, cultivates his existing capabilities and mental thinking. "Cain child is a harbinger of parental snoring, the cause of all joys, a necessary factor in the country's administration. On the contrary, the incompetent child is the ruin of the property of humanity, the darkness of parental life, a dam of the development of society," notes Obiddin Mahmudov. These are his educational conclusions that he made as a pedagogue. That is why, when raising a child, a great deal of responsibility is required from parents.[1]

We are not mistaken if we say that the president's decision on August 22, 2019 "on additional measures to further strengthen the guarantees of the rights of the child" is also a proof of how much our president is passionate about the upbringing of the future generation.

We know that our country will also be interested in growing up physically healthy, morally clean, hardworking, cultured intellectual potential of the child. No matter how well the work of educational institutions on upbringing is established, education issues are solved in the family. When kindergartens and schools teach and educate, parents not only raise, but also live with them. For this reason, the child's influence is strong and lasts longer. [2] The fact that parents are selfless for a child, this quality characteristic of Uzbek nationality is embedded in our blood. In this sense, it is desirable that we act on the basis of such criteria and rules as an individual approach to the maturation of our children, the formation of the need for mental, moral, labor education, the qualification of self-service, domestic service, spiritual and spiritual preparation for social.

The upbringing of a child has been carried out in the family since very ancient times, and it is necessary to carry out the educational process in the family at a high cultural level. The new generation has entered the XXI century, and time does not wait. Our youth lives in a highly developed environment of science, culture, art and technology. Taking into account the fact that the ideas of Eastern thinkers are combined with folk wisdom in educational issues, it is important that the attitude of parents to the upbringing of children reflects their thoughts on family interaction, caring for the elderly and children, teaching children to work from a small age. At the time of the formation and development of a child's speech in the family, they are imbued with the concepts of respect for adults, friendship, honesty, humanity. Note that at the same time they bury those around them in different questions and will remain programmable in their future life, no matter what the answers they receive. Just as well as during their daily chores in the family, children's behavior is formed, and then their processes, such as complex forms of morality: public, patriotic, international, continue. The family matures the personality of the child with all his way of life, even with small eye-catching sides.[4]

Of great importance is the fact that parents form in their children a sense of purposefulness, immersion, responsibility for work. Also, the task is to prepare the girls for family life as they get older, to carefully prepare them for the norms of etiquette, traditions, family chores and delicate spheres of life in a new family, and also requires a lot of work in the family, especially from the mother.[5] The proverb "see her mother, take her daughter" is also not in vain. Many mothers are well aware of how strong or delicate their family will be when the children start an independent family, as well as how well-being depends on the upbringing that the girls have taken in their families. Since the initial upbringing began in the family, the French

thinker J.J. Rousseau argued that “early upbringing is important of all things and is the responsibility of women.” That is why it is so important to prepare our expectant mothers, daughters for an independent life. That is why upbringing in the family is also significant for the development and future of our motherland.

References:

1. G'.B.Shoumarov, I.O.Haydarov N.A.Sog'inov "Oila psixologiyasi" Toshkent 2015-yil
2. Malla Ochilov "Muallim qalb memori" Toshkent O'qituvchi 2001-yil
3. 2019-yil 22-avgustdagi "Bola huquqlari kafolatlarini yanada kuchaytirishga oid qo'shimcha chora-tadbirlar to'g'risida "gi qarori Toshkent shahri 2019-yil.
4. . Quvvatova M. "Scientific methodical journal of" The role and importance of the family in the formation of ecological culture in preschool children. 209-2010-b.[3]
5. M.H Quvvatova, Sh. Alisherova Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning nutqini o'stirishda lug'at ishining ahamiyati - Eurasian Journal of Academic , 2022 - in-academy.uz [1]
6. Mohira Kuvvatova "Development of students' creativity as a psychological and pedagogical problem" web of scientist: international scientific research journal 10.10.2022 [2]
7. Berdiyeva M.M "Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni kasbga yo'naltirish orqali ijtimoiy rivojlanish" Ta'lim va innovatsion tadqiqotlar 10.10.2022 216-219 [4]
8. Berdiyeva M.M "The development of cognitive interests in older Preschoolers in the process of getting acquainted With nature" ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal ISSN: 2249-7137 Vol. 12, Issue SJIF 2022 = 8.252 A peer reviewed journal[5]

